

Emerging Trends in Chemical Engineering

HOME ABOUT LOGIN REGISTER SEARCH CURRENT
ARCHIVES ANNOUNCEMENTS AUTHOR GUIDELINES
REFERENCING PATTERN SAMPLE RESEARCH PAPER SAMPLE REVIEW
PAPER PUBLICATION MANAGEMENT TEAM EDITORIAL BOARD

[OPEN JOURNAL SYSTEMS](#)

[Journal Help](#)

Home > Vol 6, No 1 (2019) > **Okoye**

 Subscription or Fee Access

SUBSCRIPTION

Login to verify subscription

USER

Username

Password

Remember me

NOTIFICATIONS

- [View](#)
- [Subscribe](#)

JOURNAL CONTENT

Search

Search Scope

All

Browse

- [By Issue](#)
- [By Author](#)
- [By Title](#)
- [Other Journals](#)

FONT SIZE

INFORMATION

- [For Readers](#)
- [For Authors](#)
- [For Librarians](#)

Development of bio-based foam from *Ximenia americana* seed oil polyol: Studies on the effect of toluene diisocyanate (TDI) on some properties of the foam

S. I. Okoye, S. A. Osemeahon

Abstract

Polyurethane foam is a very important and valuable industrial product. In this study, polyol synthesized from *Ximenia americana* seed oil was used in the production of bio-based polyurethane foam. Different amounts (2mL, 4mL, 6mL, 8mL and 10mL) of toluene diisocyanate (TDI) were used in the formulation of the foams, and the effect of the varied amount of TDI was investigated by studying the foams' properties such as the density, tensile strength, compression set value, elongation at break, support factor and the hardness. Foam formed using 8 mL TDI exhibited optimum properties and this is attributed to defragmentation of the polymer matrix in the foam at TDI amounts higher than 8 mL. Bio-based foam produced in this study compares competitively with commercial foam standards. This study therefore presents the potentials of *X. americana* seed oil polyol as a sustainable product with valuable industrial application in the production of bio-based polyurethane foam

Keyword: Biobased foam, *X.americana* seed oil, polyol, toluene diisocyanate.

Full Text:

[PDF](#)

References

Nicholson J. W. (1997). The Chemistry of Polymers (2nd Edition). The Royal Society of Chemistry, Athelstan Press, London, 133-136.

Rojek M. and Stabik J. (2009). The Influence of X-Rays on Strength Properties of Polyester Vascular System Prosthesis. Journal of Achievements in Materials and Manufacturing Engineering, 35(1), 47-54.

Abdessalem, S. B., Mokhtar, S., Belaïssia, H., Filali, N., & Durand, B. (2005). Mechanical behavior of a textile polyester vascular prosthesis: theoretical and experimental study. Textile research journal, 75(11), 784-788.

Simpson R. (2004). Polymer development. The Road Map, TCE Today.

Ogunleye O.O., Oyawale F.A. and Odewole G.A. (2006). Optimum Allocation of Silicone Oil in the Flexible Polyurethane Foam Production. Journal of Science Engineering and Technology, 8(19)

Edoga M.O. and Egila E.A. (2008). Development and Characterization of Flexible Polyurethane Foam: Part I—Physicochemical and mechanochemical properties. Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences, 3(8)647

- Boldiš, M., Gašparík, M., Gaff, M., & Ruman, D. (2016). Compression set of PU foam mattresses with self-clamping joints and sandwich structure. *Wood Research*, 61(6), 1003-1016.
- Soppi, E., Lehtiö, J., & Saarinen, H. (2015). An overview of polyurethane foams in higher specification foam mattresses. *Ostomy/wound management*, 61(2), 38-46.
- Polyurethane Foam Association. Joint Industry Foam Standards and Guidelines, Sections 1, 2 and 4. 1994. Available at: www.pfa.org/jifsg. Accessed March 13, 2014
- Kurańska, M., & Prociak, A. (2016). The influence of rapeseed oil-based polyols on the foaming process of rigid polyurethane foams. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 89, 182-187.
- Fang, Z., Ji, D., He, W., Luo, Z., Jiang, X., Wang, T., & Guo, K. (2015). Polyurethane rigid foams formed from different soy-based polyols by the ring opening of epoxidised soybean oil with methanol, phenol, and cyclohexanol. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 74, 76-82.
- Pillai, P. K., Li, S., Bouzidi, L., & Narine, S. S. (2016). Metathesized palm oil polyol for the preparation of improved bio-based rigid and flexible polyurethane foams. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 83, 568-576.
- EN ISO 1798, 2008: Flexible cellular polymeric materials - Determination of tensile strength and elongation at break.
- EN ISO 1856, 2001: Flexible cellular polymeric materials - Determination of compression set.
- EN ISO 2439, 2008: Flexible cellular polymeric materials - Determination of hardness (indentation technique).
- Gama, N.V., Soares, B., Freire, C.S.R., Silva, R., Neto, C.P., Barros-Timmons, A., Ferreira, A., 2015: Bio-based polyurethane foams toward applications beyond thermal insulation. *Materials & Design* 76: 77-85, DOI: 10.1016/j.matdes.2015.03.032.
- Alzoubi, M.F, Al-Hallaj, S., Abu-Ayyad, M., 2014: Modeling of compression curves of flexible polyurethane foam with variable density, chemical formulations and strain rates. *Journal of Solid Mechanics* 6(1): 82-97.
- Faruk, O., Sain, M., Farnood, R., Pan, Y., Yiao, H., 2014: Development of lignin and nanocellulose enhanced bio PU foams for automotive parts. *Journal of Polymers and the Environment* 22(3): 279-288, DOI: 10.1007/s10924-013-0631-x
- Krishnamurthi, B., Bharadwaj-Somaskandan, S., Sergeeva, T., & Shutov, F. (2003). Effect of wood flour fillers on density and mechanical properties of polyurethane foams. *Cellular polymers*, 22(6), 371-381.
- Billmeyer, Jnr. F. W. (2005); *Textbook of Polymer Science*; 3rd edition, John Wiley and Sons, Toronto, p.447.
- Arshanitsa, A., Paberza, A., Vevere, L., Cabulis, U., & Telysheva, G. (2014, May). Two approaches for introduction of wheat straw lignin into rigid polyurethane foams. In *AIP Conference Proceedings* (Vol. 1593, No. 1, pp. 388-391). AIP.
- Petrovic Z, Guo A, Javni I. Process for the preparation of vegetable oil based polyol and electroinsulating casting compounds created from vegetable oil based polyol. *United State Patent*. 2003; 6: 573p, 354p.
- Kirpluks, M., Cābulis, U., Kurańska, M., & Prociak, A. (2013). Three different approaches for polyol synthesis from rapeseed oil. In *Key Engineering Materials* (Vol. 559, pp. 69-74). Trans Tech Publications.
- Fridrihsone, A., Stirna, U., Lazdiņa, B., Misāne, M., & Vilsone, D. (2013). Characterization of polyurethane networks structure and properties based on rapeseed oil derived polyol. *European Polymer Journal*, 49(6), 1204-1214.
- Cabulis, U., Sevastyanova, I., Andersons, J., & Beverte, I. (2014). Rapeseed oil-

based rigid polyisocyanurate foams modified with nanoparticles of various type. *Polimery*, 59(3), 207-212.

Malewska, E., Bąk, S., & Prociak, A. (2015). Effect of different concentration of rapeseed-oil-based polyol and water on structure and mechanical properties of flexible polyurethane foams. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, 132(35).

Lozada, Z., Suppes, G. J., Hsieh, F. H., Lubguban, A., & Tu, Y. C. (2009). Preparation of polymerized soybean oil and soy-based polyols. *Journal of applied polymer science*, 112(4), 2127-2135.

Tanaka, R., Hirose, S., & Hatakeyama, H. (2008). Preparation and characterization of polyurethane foams using a palm oil-based polyol. *Bioresource Technology*, 99(9), 3810-3816.

Osemeahon S.A. and Okoye S.I. (2018). Synthesis, Physicochemical and FTIR Characterization of Vegetable Oil-Based Polyol from *Ximenia americana* Seed Oil. *Journal of Modern Chemistry and Chemical Technology*, 9(3), 23-28.

Prociak, A., Malewska, E., & Bąk, S. (2016). Influence of isocyanate index on selected properties of flexible polyurethane foams modified with various bio-components. *Journal of Renewable Materials*, 4(1), 78-85.

Refbacs

- There are currently no rebfacs.